

PERFECTING APPROACHES TO PERSONNEL RECRUITMENT IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

Elena Nikolskaya*, Elena Zakharova**, Natalia Avilova***, Alla Kononova**** & Olga Dmitrieva*****

Abstract

The purpose of the article is to develop a recommendation system for hospitality enterprises using non-traditional forms of recruitment. The dynamism of changes in the environment is found to necessitate the use of innovative approaches based on the real needs and opportunities of modern hospitality industry enterprises. It is confirmed that the effectiveness of personnel recruitment depends on the mastery of up-to-date methods. It is established that implementing the totality of the proposed modern human resource management technologies will contribute to increased personnel productivity and efficiency of hotel enterprises. The introduction and implementation of innovative technologies of personnel management are found to bring changes to other resource areas – in the nature of the hotel product, in the way relationships with the key customers are constructed, and in the economy of the hotel enterprise as a whole in a digitalized environment.

Keywords: Recruitment; Hotel business; Management; Innovation; Hotel product.

APERFEIÇOAMENTO DE ABORDAGENS PARA O RECRUTAMENTO DE PESSOAL NA INDÚSTRIA HOTELEIRA

Resumo

O objetivo do artigo é desenvolver um sistema de recomendação para empresas de hospitalidade usando formas não tradicionais de recrutamento. O dinamismo das mudanças no ambiente exige o uso de abordagens inovadoras baseadas nas reais necessidades e oportunidades das empresas modernas da indústria hoteleira. Confirma-se que a eficácia do recrutamento de pessoal depende do domínio de métodos atualizados. Fica estabelecido que a implementação da totalidade das modernas tecnologias de gestão de recursos humanos propostas contribuirá para o aumento da produtividade do pessoal e da eficiência das empresas hoteleiras. A introdução e implementação de tecnologias inovadoras de gestão de pessoal trazem mudanças para outras áreas de recursos – na natureza do produto hoteleiro, na forma como os relacionamentos com os principais clientes são construídos e na economia da empresa hoteleira como um todo em um ambiente digitalizado.

Palavras-chave: Recrutamento; Hotelaria; Gestão; Inovação; Produto hoteleiro.

PERFECCIONAR LOS ENFOQUES DE LA CONTRATACIÓN DE PERSONAL EN EL SECTOR DE LA HOSTELERÍA

Resumen

El objetivo del artículo es desarrollar un sistema de recomendación para empresas de hostelería que utilicen formas de contratación no tradicionales. Se considera que el dinamismo de los cambios en el entorno requiere el uso de enfoques innovadores basados en las necesidades y oportunidades reales de las empresas modernas de la industria hotelera. Se confirma que la eficacia de la contratación de personal depende del dominio de los métodos actualizados. Se establece que la implementación de la totalidad de las tecnologías modernas de gestión de recursos humanos propuestas contribuirá a aumentar la productividad del personal y la eficiencia de las empresas hoteleras. Se encuentra que la introducción e implementación de tecnologías innovadoras de gestión de personal trae cambios a otras áreas de recursos: en la naturaleza del producto hotelero, en la forma en que se construyen las relaciones con los clientes clave y en la economía de la empresa hotelera en su conjunto. en un entorno digitalizado.

Palabras clave: Contratación; Hostelería; Gestión; Innovación; Producto hotelero.

1 INTRODUCTION

The most efficient use of personnel is one of the major factors in the success of a hotel business enterprise. In this case, the staff is the key resource that determines the performance of the hotel business as a whole. Thus, there arises a need for human resource management capable of forming an environment in which labor potential will be effectively realized, the abilities of employees will develop, and the level of satisfaction with their work will grow (Deng et al., 2022).

However, the level of work with personnel currently does not comply with the tasks of the fundamental restructuring of management and the implementation of an active social and personnel policy in the hotel business (Gürlek, Tuna, 2019). Scientific methods of assessment, placement, and training of personnel using the results of scientific research are insufficiently introduced into the practice of personnel services of hotel enterprises.

Therefore, efficient personnel selection is especially critical for each hotel enterprise since rational equipment with staff determines their

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* Candidate of Economic Sciences, Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, 36 Stremyanny Lane, Moscow, 117997, Russia. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0972-1069, e-mail: nikolskaya@gmail.com

** Candidate of Economic Sciences, Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, 36 Stremyanny Lane, Moscow, 117997, Russia. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9759-7610, e-mail: e-elena55@mail.ru

*** Doctor of Historic Sciences, Russian State University of Physical Culture, Sports, Youth and Tourism (SCOLIPE), 4 Sirenevsky Boulevard, Moscow, 105122, Russia. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-1695-0057, e-mail: avilova_nl@mail.ru

**** Candidate of Legal Sciences, Vyatka State University, 36 Moskovskaya str., Kirov, 610000, Russia. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5834-3215, e-mail: usr11587@vyatsu.ru

***** Candidate of Economic Sciences, Moscow Polytechnic University, 38 Bolshaya Semenovskaya str., Moscow, 107023, Russia. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-8328-3971, e-mail: ovdmitrieva@yandex.ru

efficiency, competitiveness, and, naturally, profitability. This shapes the relevance of developing and using new personnel selection technologies at hotel enterprises (Afridi et al., 2020).

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The problems of the development of hospitality businesses are explored in the works of A.A. Belaia (2017), G.P. Gagarinskaia (2017), A.A. Galochkin (2019), M.M.K. Gukasova (2018), Ia.V. Kulakova (2016), P.G. Nikolenko (2017), etc. However, the issues of perfecting the approaches to personnel selection in the hotel business remain understudied.

For example, Belaia (2017, p. 71) believes that personnel management is a continuous process of solving the problem of staffing a hotel enterprise with personnel of the appropriate quality and quantity, which requires the performance of certain tasks: recruitment, selection, career management, employee adaptation, personnel assessment, etc.

We can agree with the opinion of Gagarinskaia (2017) who defines the selection of personnel of a hotel enterprise as a process of studying the psychological and professional qualities of an employee to establish their compliance with the requirements of the workplace and select from the available applicants the one who is most suitable for this workplace, considering their qualifications, specialty, personal qualities, abilities, character, and the interests of the hotel enterprise.

According to Galochkin (2019, p. 162), recruitment is "a process of studying the professional and psychological qualities of an employee, caused by the need to establish their ability to perform specific duties at a particular workplace and select from a set of potential employees those who are able to meet the needs of a hotel enterprise".

Gukasova notes that selection is the decision to enroll candidates who, according to test results, are more likely to be suitable for future activities in a hotel enterprise (2018, p. 623).

Kulakova emphasizes that cost savings in the hotel business are associated with factors that affect the results of the service activities of a hotel company, as well as the financial aspects of the hotel business (2016, p. 141).

Nikolaenko (2017) rightly writes that the concentration of efforts of the personnel department contributes to the development of demand for IT products, due to which the recruitment process in the hotel business is possible.

The reliability of the described approaches is supported by the fact that competition in the labor market forces hospitality industry enterprises to search for new unconventional approaches to personnel recruitment – to organize open house days, hold competitions and internships (Lukiyanchuk, Panasenko, Kazantseva, Lebedev, & Lebedeva,

2020; Nikolskaya et al., 2021; Zavalko, Kozhina, Zhakevich, Matyunina, & Lebedeva, 2017). These activities are united by the general concept of event-recruiting. Event-recruiting refers to the attraction of candidates for vacant positions by means of special events that are profitable for the hotel enterprise both financially and in terms of improving its public image (Pimentel, 2020).

This approach is most often used to attract young specialists mainly for entry-level positions that are not attractive for experienced professionals. Event-recruiting is advisable to be used to save money and create a positive image of the hotel enterprise in the employment market if the enterprise has at least five open positions.

3 METHODS

The study was carried out based on Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, Russian State University of Physical Culture, Sports, Youth and Tourism, Vyatka State University and Moscow Polytechnic University in 2021-2022. To solve this problem, we used general scientific and special research methods.

The methodological basis of the study is constructed by the following general scientific methods: analysis and synthesis in the analysis of the existing theoretical and methodological approaches and provisions and scientific developments on the issues of personnel selection for the hospitality industry; the structural-logical method used in the systematization of the factors influencing personnel potential in the hotel business.

The selection of sources was carried out considering the current state of the hospitality industry. We used legislative and regulatory acts, materials of state agencies and local authorities, and scientific publications of Russian and foreign scholars on the selection of personnel in the hospitality industry.

The selection of sources was carried out within the industry specifics of hotel enterprises (Agamirova, et al, 2017; Markova et al, 2021; Ogloblina, et al, 2020). Special attention was paid to scientific articles related to the selection of personnel in the hotel business.

Special methods include an expert survey of heads of hospitality industry enterprises in the Russian Federation, conducted in 2021. We used a questionnaire, which included questions on event recruiting; 47 participants were interviewed, including managers and leading specialists of hotel businesses.

In the course of this study, we intend to develop approaches to analyzing the problems of personnel selection in the hospitality industry and substantiate the action strategies of participants in the hospitality business in personnel recruitment. Another objective involves providing substantiation for the approaches to personnel assessment and formulating the main

directions of human resources development in modern conditions.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Characterize the context and object of study

The study results show that new objects are appearing on the market that combine comfortable and interesting accommodation, vivid tourist impressions, and a well-thought-out recreation format. An important step towards the development of the hotel business is the creation of year-round facilities. For example, glamping, which allows one to relax in nature all year round just a few hours' drive from Moscow.

There is also a project that gives one the opportunity to discover the beauty and uniqueness of northern nature, combined with comfortable accommodation and a variety of active entertainment programs. These projects will actively appear in the

near future, although the basis of the hotel offer will be the objects already created earlier.

In addition, the hotel business within the Russian Federation is undergoing an active stage of development, new attractive projects have already appeared, and the development of entire resorts has been launched. If we talk about shorter-term trends, then in the near future we can observe a gradual process of changing hotel brands and names.

For 2017-2021 period, the number of employees in hotels and similar accommodation facilities in Russia increased by 17.6% and in 2021 amounted to 266.1 thousand people. In 2020, the coronavirus pandemic led to a significant reduction in staff in the hotel business – by 10.1% compared to 2019.

Hotels were forced to refuse to hire seasonal staff and cut permanent employees to reduce costs during the period of forced downtime. In 2021, the number of employees in the hotel industry recovered by 4.0% but did not reach the level of 2019 (Table 1).

Table 1. Number of staff in the hospitality industry in the Russian Federation for 2017-2021

Indicators	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Average number of all employees in the hospitality industry, thousand people	226.2	260.1	284.5	255.8	266.1
Percentage to the previous year, %	-	14.9	9.4	-10.1	4.0

Source: Federal State Statistics Service of the Russian Federation

In 2021, the absence of migrants and the lack of prestige of the profession did not allow fully compensating for the lack of staff. Even the forced increase in salaries did not contribute to the influx of applicants. Before the pandemic, competition for vacancies was at the level of five people per position on average in Russia. At the peak of the first wave of the pandemic due to a hiring freeze and layoffs in May 2020, competition rose to 16 resumes per position.

By September 2021, there were already only 1.7 resumes per vacancy. Not all migrants who before the pandemic worked in the positions of lower line personnel (auxiliary workers, washers, baggage handlers, cleaners, and maids) were able to return to Russia. In addition to this, there is a redistribution of labor resources in the market. Several industries, such as the construction industry or retail, offer employees higher wages than hotels, and there is an outflow of personnel.

In addition, the pandemic has also caused a regional turnover of employees. Hotels in some

regions, for example in the Urals, have closed or reduced staff. As a result, workers have left for places where they were more in demand, for example, in the resort regions of the Krasnodar Territory.

In this context, human resource management is a continuous process of solving the problems of staffing hospitality businesses with personnel of sufficient quality and quantity, which requires solving certain objectives: recruitment, selection, career management, employee adaptation, and personnel assessment (Nedosugova, Khairullina, Baranova, Shugaeva, Korotaeva, 2021).

Meanwhile, personnel selection implies a process of studying the personal and professional qualities of employees to assure their compliance with the job requirements and select applicants who are best suited for the job, taking into account their qualifications, specialty, personal qualities, abilities, and the nature and interests of the hospitality industry. All this is guided by certain principles and criteria (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Principles and criteria of personnel selection in a hotel establishment

Source: own elaboration.

Moreover, personnel selection involves the process of exploring the professional and psychological characteristics of an employee for the purpose of determining their ability to perform specific duties at a particular job and selecting from the pool of potential employees those who are able to meet the needs of the hotel company.

Further on, personnel selection involves making the decision to hire candidates who show the signs of fitness for further activities as a result of testing. Recently, a number of new unconventional approaches to personnel selection have appeared in global practice. One of these forms of work is staff leasing.

In this case, staff leasing or staff on loan is a management technology that allows supplying the business process of hotel businesses with human resources using the services of a third-party organization. In addition, there are three main reasons that justify outsourcing:

- cost savings – the cost of personnel services of the hotel business is reduced since such services are cheaper and the number of employees in a particular division of the company can be reduced;
- concentration of efforts of the human resources department – employees of the department are not distracted from the key tasks that bring added value;

- gaining special knowledge – it is possible to obtain know-how and special knowledge not available at the hotel business enterprise.

Apart from that, the effective activity of a modern hotel business enterprise is determined by many factors, among which the human factor is of great importance. We have proved that only those enterprises of the hotel business, in which the most high-quality human resources are concentrated, function constantly. Therefore, hotel enterprises face the need to solve complex problems, first of all, the search for and recruitment of highly qualified personnel.

Many enterprises operating in the market of hotel services cannot use the traditional forms of recruitment to solve such problems as the reduction of the budget item of personnel expenses, high turnover of personnel due to changes in compensation policy, seasonal hiring of personnel, and the need for specialists, whose services are not common in the market. Therefore, it can be proposed to use a recruitment system that includes strategic planning (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Recruitment system at a hospitality industry enterprise

Source: own elaboration.

Moreover, the need for personnel in the hospitality industry may arise on a regular basis. At the same time, the specialists' areas of expertise may lie in accounting, marketing, or the law. In addition, the temporary need is usually met with the company's own resources through distributing new responsibilities among the available employees. This strategy, however, inevitably entails a decrease in the productivity of the entire hotel enterprise, because an employee cannot perform additional duties at a proper level for an extended period of time, while also staying efficient in performing their standard duties.

Given that seasonal fluctuations are typical of the hotel services market, during the peak periods, businesses need personnel, and their staff may double depending on the level of demand for the service. Hotel businesses are then faced with a situation in which hiring new employees is unprofitable, yet the work must be done professionally and on time.

For example, an additional need for lower-level management staff may be 3-5 people (hall administrators, waiters, standard cooks, bartenders) for an approximate period of 1-3 months. Thus, staff leasing will be irreplaceable in case of a need to perform final works requiring high qualification, for example, in the case of the internal audit of a hotel enterprise. Thus, there is no need to hire an employee and then wonder what they will do once the audit is completed.

4.2 Data Presentation

The results of conducted research indicate that 53% of the surveyed executives of the hospitality industry enterprises report the shortage of qualified personnel – specialists with the necessary skills. In addition, 64% of the respondents indicated that, the enterprises are in need of specialists, the services of which have no analogs in the market (for example, serving VIP-persons). However, finding a qualified specialist for temporary employment in a short time is quite problematic.

Leasing can also be successfully used to perform regular, but not resource-intensive procedures, as 75% believed. For example, such activities may be the maintenance of the hotel enterprise computer system and communication facilities, or record keeping. For small hotel enterprises, this service will be of major importance, because a small hotel enterprise may not have vacancies for individual specialists.

In the meantime, the effectiveness of a hotel enterprise is contingent on the accurately selected type of leasing, as 83% believe. In this, the recruitment of temporary personnel will correspond to the leasing companies providing temporary and seasonal personnel for the short term. This type of

staff leasing allows meeting the need for staff during the seasonal increased workload. The advantages of this type of leasing include the opportunity to quickly recruit the necessary worker for a short period of time, the lack of costs for finding temporary workers, no expenses for personnel records and the administration of all types of operating costs, and the possibility of terminating cooperation in the short term.

Staff leasing also includes providing the client companies with workers from the agency's staff for a relatively long period of time (from three months to several years). This service of leasing agencies is best used by the hospitality industry when there is a need to hire temporary workers in certain categories.

In this case, it is possible to equip certain departments or divisions with staff in a short period of time. In addition, the enterprise can consider outsourcing, which implies that the hotel enterprise delegates part of its non-core functions to an external provider. In either case, the external provider performs the service, but the service is purchased regularly, and the provider's employees work on the hotel enterprise's premises using its derivative funds and for its benefit.

The peculiarity of outsourcing is that the contract between the company that provides outsourcing services and the hotel enterprise does not clearly stipulate the possibility of transferring the employee to the staff of the enterprise. In addition to these directions of the use of leasing, the management of a hospitality enterprise can use leasing in a number of other cases: if the volume of hotel occupancy goes down; if there is a desire to increase the sales of additional services; in the case of promotions and bonuses being introduced, if these innovations need to be delivered faster than the customers learn about them through classic means of advertisement.

Furthermore, in their practice, hospitality industry enterprises sometimes face situations when several vacancies remain unfilled. In this case, the human resources department of the hotel enterprise receives a large flow of resumes from potential candidates that need to be selected for the next stages. In our view, the best tool, in this case, is the use of automated recruitment systems.

However, automated recruitment systems imply scanning candidates' resumes by certain criteria. These criteria are strictly followed, and the system will never offer a candidate that does not meet the set parameters to a tee. The employer can set any parameters they wish – from the worker's experience to information from previous employment.

The analysis allows the system to score candidates' resumes in points. Candidates whose scores are too low usually do not qualify for the next round. After this analysis of resumes, the work is continued by the human resources department of the hotel enterprise. Thus, the automated recruitment

system can significantly save the time of the hotel enterprise's human resources specialists, who are physically unable to keep track of the questionnaires of the many candidates for a vacant position.

Nevertheless, it must be noted that a major drawback of the scanning systems is the risk of losing a fitting candidate. If a candidate does not complete their resume, miss a certain keyword, or forgets to clarify something important, the system will likely filter them out, and the hotel enterprise can lose a worker it needs.

Given the active development of information technology, the process of personnel selection and recruitment in the hospitality industry becomes more automated. In this case, information about applicants can be made available to human resources specialists through a variety of portals and online interviewing platforms, but also through the use of social media, video conferencing, and viewing candidates' videos. One variation of this approach is the video resume.

Video resumes are an unusual type of presenting information about a candidate that gives the employer an opportunity to spot and select vibrant and outstanding personalities and allows the candidate to best highlight their strengths and present their way of thinking and personality in the best light. However, video resumes cannot replace the traditional means of communication with employers, they can only supplement them and help to get a better position compared to other applicants.

4.3 Discussion

Our conclusions differ from those of Belaia (2017), Gagarińskaia (2017), Galochkin (2019), Gukasova (2018), Kulakova (2016), Nikolenko (2017), and others who note that to attract the necessary personnel, it is important for a hotel company that candidates receive not only general information about the hotel on its website, but also have a clear idea of its corporate culture, the history of its creation, and prospects for further development and, therefore, of the opportunities for their own growth.

However, our research highlights that to attract employees for entry-level positions, a rather effective way for hospitality industry companies is to create their own promotional resource addressed to young professionals.

At the same time, internal PR campaigns aimed at attracting potential employees mean an introduction to the hotel company that determines not only the willingness of the applicant to accept the proposed contract terms, enter the company, and gain a foothold in it, but also the desire to support and spread the company's positive image (Ahmad et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2018).

In addition, the proposed approaches to the selection of personnel in the hotel business make it possible to evaluate the development indicators of

hotel enterprises, determine the values of managerial factors, and identify the level of the personnel management system, considering personnel leasing, through which it is possible to satisfy the need for workers during seasonal workload (Darvishmotevali et al., 2020; Dedeoğlu et al., 2018).

To draw a summary, world experience has accumulated a considerable range of personnel selection and recruitment methods. However, the dynamism of changes in the environment calls for innovative approaches based on the real needs and opportunities of modern hospitality industry enterprises (Lapointe et al., 2021).

In the meantime, the effectiveness of personnel recruitment depends on the mastery of modern methods, which is why it is advisable that their development is monitored. The advantages of staff leasing as a relatively new method of meeting the need for temporary staff are apparent and have proven to be useful in many leading world countries.

Furthermore, the implementation of the totality of the proposed modern technologies of human resources management will promote greater efficiency of hotel enterprises. The implementation of innovative human resource management technologies in hotel enterprises is relevant since they will also bring changes to other resource areas – in the nature of the hotel product, in the way relationships with the key customers are constructed, and in the economy of the hotel enterprise as a whole.

5 CONCLUSION

In the course of the study, we determined that the leasing of employees means providing a hotel enterprise for a relatively long period of workers who are on the staff of the agency. It is better to use this service of leasing agencies to enterprises in the hospitality industry when there is a need to hire temporary workers of certain categories.

Another profitable option is outsourcing, which provides the possibility of transferring an employee to the staff of a hotel enterprise. The management of a hotel enterprise can also use leasing in a number of other cases: the volume of hotel occupancy has declined; in case of the desire to increase sales volumes of additional services; the introduction of promotions and bonuses, if these innovations need to be conveyed faster than customers learn about them through classic advertising media.

In addition, the development of information technology ensures the automation of the process of searching and hiring personnel for hospitality industry enterprises. In this case, information about applicants can be made available to HR professionals through not only a variety of portals and online interview opportunities but also through the use of social networks, videoconferencing, and viewing videos about candidates.

Prospects for further research should include proposals for the development of a personnel selection system, a culture of personnel management, the integration of a personnel selection system into the management process, as well as the determination of an optimal incentive system for hotel employee

REFERENCES

- Afridi, S.A., Afsar, B., Shahjehan, A., Khan, W., Rehman, Z.U., Khan, M.A. (2020). Impact of corporate social responsibility attributions on employee's extra-role behaviors: moderating role of ethical corporate identity and interpersonal trust. *Corp. Soc. Responsib. Environ. Manag.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2017>
- Agamirova, Ek.V., Agamirova, El.V., Lebedeva, O Ye., Lebedev, K.A., & Ilkevich, S.V. (2017). Methodology of estimation of quality of tourist product. *Quality - Access to Success*, 18(157), 82-84.
- Ahmad, N., Ullah, Z., Aldhaen, E., Han, H., Araya-Castillo, L., & Ariza-Montes, A. (2022). Fostering Hotel-Employee Creativity Through Micro-Level Corporate Social Responsibility: A Social Identity Theory Perspective. *Frontiers in psychology*, 13, 853125. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.853125>
- Belaia, A.A. (2017). Vsestonnnaia otsenka raboty personala otelia [Comprehensive assessment of hotel staff]. *Modern Scientific Researches and Innovations*, 5(73), 71.
- Darvishmotevali, M., Altinay, L., Köseoglu, M.A. (2020). The link between environmental uncertainty, organizational agility, and organizational creativity in the hotel industry. *Int. J. Hosp. Manag.*, 87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102499>
- Dedeoğlu, B.B., Aydin, Ş. Boğan, E. (2018). The role of the employees in the innovation of the hotel enterprises. *An. Bras. Estud. Turísticos-ABET*, 8, 85–99. <https://doi.org/10.34019/2238-2925.2018.v8.13879>
- Deng, Y., Cherian, J., Ahmad, N., Scholz, M., Samad, S. (2022). Conceptualizing the role of target-specific environmental transformational leadership between corporate social responsibility and pro-environmental behaviors of hospital employees. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19063565>
- Gagarinskaia, G.P., Kuznetsova, I.G., Gagarinskii, A.V., & Samanchin, B.T. (2017). Strategiiia upravleniia personalom sfery gostinichnykh uslug [Strategy of personnel management in the field of hotel services]. *Journal of the Kyrgyz State Technical University named after I. Razzakov*, 4(44), 459-469.
- Galochkin, A.A. (2019). Model kompetentsii dlia podbora kontaktnogo personala otelia [Competency model for selecting hotel contact staff]. *Young Scientist*, 16(254), 161-169.
- Gukasova, M.M.K. (2018). Problemy obucheniia i razvitiia personala v rossiiskikh setevykh oteliakh [Problems of personnel training and development in Russian chain hotels]. *Alley of Science*, 6(6(22)), 623-627.
- Gürlek, M., Tuna, M. (2019). Corporate social responsibility and work engagement: evidence from the hotel industry. *Tour. Manag. Perspect.*, 31, 195–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2019.05.004>
- Kulakova, Ia.V., & Odarenko, T.E. (2016). Obuchenie i razvitie personala – neobkhodimoe uslovie povysheniia effektivnosti raboty otelia [Personnel training and development – a necessary condition for improving the efficiency of a hotel]. *Tavrisheskii nauchnyi obozrevatel*, 5-1(10), 141-144.
- Lapointe, D., Guimont, D., Guillemard, A., & Benjamin, C. (2021). People, Place, Values: Living Lab as Social Innovation Processes for Tourism Communities. *Anais Brasileiros De Estudos Turísticos*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5771002>
- Lukiyanchuk, I.N., Panasenko, S.V., Kazantseva, S.Yu., Lebedev, K.A., & Lebedeva, O.E. (2020). Development of online retailing logistics flows in a globalized digital economy. *Revista Inclusiones*, 7(S2-1), 407-416.
- Markova, O.V., Listopad, E.Ye., Shelygov, A.V., Fedorov, A.G., & Kiselevich, I.V. (2021). Economic and legal aspects of the innovative activity of enterprises in the context of the digital economy. *Nexo Revista Científica*, 34(2), 964-972.
- Nedosugova, A.B., Khairullina, D.D., Baranova, E.A., Shugaeva, E.A., Korotaeva, I.E. (2021). Teaching Tourist Guides Foreign Languages: Finding Effective Methods. *Revista EntreLinguas*, 7(esp. 4). <https://doi.org/10.29051/el.v7iesp.4.15660>
- Nikolenko, P.G. (2017). Innovatsii v upravlenii personalom v gostinitse [Innovations in personnel management in a hotel]. *Bulletin of Michurinsk State Agrarian University*, 2, 82-85.
- Nikolskaya, E.Y., Fedorchukova, S.G., Kulgachev, I.P., Umarov, M.M., Yudina, E.V., & Feoktistov, S.V. (2021). The impact of organizational culture on the strategic development of tourism and hospitality enterprises. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 20(4), 1-9.
- Ogloblina, E.V., Seredina, M.I., Altunina, J.O., Kodolov, V.A., & Lebedev, K.A. (2020). Socio-economic consequences of digital development of the economy. *Revista Inclusiones*, 7(Especial), 421-430.
- Pimentel, T. D. (2020). The Tourism Field: a socio-political perspective to study the action and its structuring. *Latin American Journal of Tourismology*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.34019/2448-198X.2020.v6.33132>
- Wang, T.-C., Tang, T.-W., Cheng, J.-S. (2018). Art-oriented model of hotel service innovation. *Int. J. Contemp. Hosp. Manag.*, 30, 160–177. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-02-2016-0059>
- Zavalko, N.A., Kozhina, V.O., Zhakevich, A.G., Matyunina, O.E., & Lebedeva, O.Ye. (2017). Methodical approaches to rating the quality of financial control at the enterprise. *Quality - Access to Success*, 18(161), 69-72.

Table 1. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	A.2	A.3	A.4	A.5
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+		+	+	+

Term	Definition	Author 1	A.2	A.3	A.4	A.5
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	+	+	+		+
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components		+	+		+
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	+	+		+	+
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	+	+		+	+
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	+	+	+		+
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	+		+		+
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+	+	+	+	+
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	+		+		+
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages	+		+	+	+
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	+	+		+	+
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team		+	+	+	+
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	+		+		+
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	+	+	+	+	+

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

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